

Positional bias in variant calls against draft reference assemblies

Roman V. Briskine¹ and Kentaro K. Shimizu^{1,2}

¹Department of Evolutionary Biology and Environmental Studies, University of Zurich, Winterthurerstrasse 190, Zurich, CH-8057, Switzerland

²Kihara Institute for Biological Research, Yokohama City University, 641-12 Maioka, Totsuka-ward, Yokohama, 244-0813, Japan

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Figure S55: Distribution of positions for SNPs called against **Sim_soap_K69 scaffolds** using the actual *A. thaliana* Bs-1 reads or our simulated reads. The ‘Sim only’ row shows SNPs called only with the simulated reads, ‘Bs-1 only’ row exhibits SNPs unique to the Bs-1 alignments, while ‘Both’ row displays SNPs called individually with both Bs-1 and simulated reads. Scaffold coordinates were transformed into the contig coordinates.

Figure S56: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **contigs** in the simulated data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S57: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **contigs** in the simulated data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S58: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **scaffolds** in the simulated data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S59: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **scaffolds** in the simulated data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S60: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 5' end of contigs with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S61: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 3' end of contigs with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S62: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **contigs** in the Bs-1 data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S63: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **scaffolds** in the Bs-1 data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S64: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **scaffolds** in the Bs-1 data set with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S65: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 5' end of contigs with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S66: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 3' end of contigs with repetitive element annotation. Colour indicates whether the SNPs are within repetitive sequences (blue) or not (orange). SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments. Repetitive elements included all sequences reported by RepeatMasker.

Figure S67: Distribution of SNPs at position k in the simulated contigs by repetitive element family. The top panel shows the total number of position k SNPs within each family. The lower panel shows the proportion of repetitive element sequences that contain a SNP at position k . The proportion of SNPs in the Unknown family was high for Sim_sga_m75 due to the low total number of such sequences in the assembly, i.e. a single SNP occurrence would already yield a high proportion.

Figure S68: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **contigs** in the simulated data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S69: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **contigs** in the simulated data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S70: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **scaffolds** in the simulated data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S71: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **scaffolds** in the simulated data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S72: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 5' end of contigs after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S73: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 3' end of contigs after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the simulated read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S74: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **contigs** in the Bs-1 data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S75: Distribution of SNP positions at the 5' end of **scaffolds** in the Bs-1 data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S76: Distribution of SNP positions at the 3' end of **scaffolds** in the Bs-1 data set after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S77: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 5' end of contigs after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S78: Distribution of SNP positions **transformed** from scaffold to contig coordinates at the 3' end of contigs after repetitive element filtering. SNPs were called from the Bs-1 read alignments and SNPs located in the annotated repetitive elements were removed.

Figure S79: Intersection between SNPs called against **Sim_soap_K69 scaffolds** with the actual *A. thaliana* Bs-1 reads or our simulated reads after repetitive element filtering. Scaffold coordinates were transformed into the contig coordinates.

Figure S80: Distribution of positions for SNPs called against **Sim_soap_K69 scaffolds** after coordinate transformation and repetitive element filtering.